

HYPOTHESIS REGARDING A PRINCIPLE OF WORK OF THE PHENOMENON OF TELEPATHY**Abstract.**

In the process of working on the formation of a knowledge base, which, in the future, will be required to form a model of an artificial central nervous system, in relation to the anatomy and physiology of the central nervous system, a need arose to know a work principle of such a phenomenon as telepathy. There are assumptions that such a phenomenon is possible, but the work principle is not described. In this paper, a model of the telepathy process is proposed. The proposed model cannot be accepted without evidence.

Keywords: *phenomenon, effect, telepathy, mirror neurons, quantum entanglement, signal, information, communication, central nervous system.*

1. Introduction.

In the process of working on the formation of a knowledge base, which, in the future, will allow the formation of a model of an artificial central nervous system (ACNS, CNS) [1, 2], in relation to the anatomy and physiology of the central nervous system, a problem arose with the lack of known information regarding the work of such the system, which is in interaction with another such system (and, more, such systems) using the phenomenon of telepathy.

Briefly, the definition of the phenomenon of telepathy is the process of transmitting information between living organisms that are at some distance from each other, using a sensory system (SS), which is not included in the standard list of the sensory systems of living organisms [3, 4]. The following examples of the action of the phenomenon of telepathy, both during sleep and during wakefulness, without transmitting information about this, using the standard 5 senses, are: a premonition of some event that should happen in the future; a sense of the mood of another organism (organisms); etc.

The purpose of this work is to determine the work principle of telepathy.

2. Analysis of known information.

To date, there is some evidence regarding the phenomenon of telepathy [3-6]. However, as far as the author knows, this has not been fully proven; as well as a model of this process has not been formed.

According to the information presented in the work [7], it is possible to form an assumption that, when new connections between organisms arise, there is a possibility that their behavior can acquire a common meaning, which is also expressed in a change in the work of the organism's substances and, as a consequence, can further be expressed in a mutation of deoxyribonucleic acid (DNA).

According to the assumption, the phenomenon of telepathy can be the basis of some mental disorders - for example, schizophrenia [8]. Probably, the symptoms of dissociative identity disorder (DID), in this case, can also be achieved with the help of this phenomenon.

According to known information [9, 10], one of the hypotheses that describes the cause of the phenomenon of telepathy is the one that indicates the phenomenon of quantum entanglement. Thus, according to the

phenomenon, there can be two or more objects that have mutual dependence.

Also, there is a hypothesis that indicates that the phenomenon of telepathy is associated with the effect of "mirror neurons" [11].

In addition, there is a hypothesis regarding the work of telepathy, which is based, jointly, on two hypotheses that are given, above, in the text [12].

According to the works [13, 14], according to the phenomenon of quantum entanglement, attempts were made to form a model of this process.

In addition, there is auxiliary information, according to the works [11, 15], which describes the reasons for the improvement of the process of pattern recognition (according to "mind reading"), in the process of this. Such reasons are the improvement of the quality of the work of individual substances - for example, oxytocin.

Also, according to the works [16, 17], there is an assumption that the work of DNA is associated with the phenomenon of quantum entanglement. If this is so, then it can be assumed that the phenomenon of telepathy can, also, be justified by this, in the general system.

According to the known information, the author's conclusion is the acceptance of the existence of the phenomenon of telepathy.

One of the proofs of this phenomenon, in a simple form, is the existence of homeostasis in society, among living organisms. Each organism that adapts to current conditions is already under the influence, in the case that the organism is "naive", of the vital activity of a separate group of organisms. At the same time, the emergence and maintenance of communication occurs in an autonomous mode, of the central nervous system, which describes the work of the unconscious state. In the process of this, mutations in DNA most likely occur.

Another is the existence of positive results, in experiments, to determine the action of telepathy, such as in the work [6].

3. Telepathy process model.**3.1. Information recognition.**

Figure 1, briefly, shows the sequence of actions in the recognition process of an auditory information, such as a melody. For this figure, the following description follows: a, b and c – graphs that describe, respec-

tively, the relationship of the signal to time and the frequency spectrum of signals to time; I , t and f – the parameters, that are specified for the graphs, of the signal values, time and frequency, respectively; A – the restoration of information that was, previously, fed to the input of the auditory SS by stimuli that are not notes of a melody, using imagination; 1 – the state of information before receiving the auditory SS; 2 – the primary state (quantization), which is formed in area A1, of information; 3 – the result of information recognition using the imagination process; B – the restoration of information using a hypothesis that describes the state in which distorted information is formed at the input of the system; 1 – the state of information before receiving

the system; 2 – the primary state; 3 – the result of information recognition with the use of the hypothesis that it acts autonomously. The information that comes to the input, for both states, can be defined as noise, and, at all, not be subject to processing for recognition by the system, with an insufficient level of attention; however, in case B, for example, in schizophrenia, the information can, also, be defined as delirium, which corresponds to hallucination (which occurs in diseases that are based on mental disorders), which was formed by the system, autonomously, with the help of the additional process of imagination (own).

Figure 1. The scheme, according to the hypothesis, of recognition, in the central nervous system, of auditory information, by feeding several signals to the input of the system. Description, of the figure, see the text.

As is known, when, for example, two or more signals are arrive to the input of the auditory SS in turn, which may represent individual frequencies (or groups of frequencies, where one frequency is highlighted),

which may not be notes of a melody, in the CNS, with the additional help of the imagination, can be transformed into a melody, which, due to some reasons – for

example, a disrupted work of substances, under standard conditions, was impossible to reproduce. This is shown with the help of an illustration in Figure 1.A.

If this is so, then, in the CNS, for association needs, only, two or more signals, which are transmitted in turn, which then, in the process of processing, with the help of recognition (hypothesis or imagination) of information of a less difficult type, is transformed, for the purpose of awareness by the organism, into information of a more difficult type – for example, a word (speech), which can be registered in the area that relates to the auditory SS, the brain cerebral cortex (B CC, CC). This is shown in Figure 1.B. The activation sequences of the areas (Brodmann areas (BA)), of the B CC, for individual information processing functions, known and hypothesized, regarding this, are given, in the table, below. For this table the following description

follows: the underlined text defining a separate area that refers to the pathway describing the imagination process of one's own (initiative) type, not autonomous, thinking; Hc – the hippocampus; n – the current value of the number of stimuli (it should, also, be taken into account that as a result of quantization of signals in time, the number of these, always, matters more, for the SS) that arrive at the input of the auditory SS; i – the total value of the number of stimuli that constitute the melody. Actually, the function describing “recognition of a part and/or all – in full, information with use imagination process”, which is given in the table, corresponds to the illustration in Figure 1.A; the function “recognition of information with use hypothesis” – to Figure 1.B.

Table.

Sequence of activation of the areas of the B CC during transmission of auditory information, for separate functions.

Function	Sequence of areas (BA) of the B CC
Rapid information recognition	41; 42; 22; (21)
Information recognition with use the semantic process	41; 42; 22; (21); 45;
Saving information	41; 42; 22; (21); 36 (35); 34; Hc
Reproduction of information with use imagination process	<u>6; 44; (44/45); 22</u> [18] (37 (19), for visual system, [19])
Recognition (and reproduction) of information with use hypothesis	41; 42; 22; 45; 47; 10; 10; 46 (9/46); 47; 45; 44; 22;
Recognition of information with use imagination process, in real time (with time delay)	{ 41; 42; 22; 45; } x n , where $n = 1, 2, \dots, i$ 47; 10; <u>10; 46; (9/46); 10;</u> { 41; 42; 22; <u>6; 44; (44/45); 22</u> } x n , where $n = 1, 2, \dots, i$
Recognition of part and/or all – in full, information with use imagination process	{ 41; 42; 22; 45; } x n , where $n = 1, 2, \dots, i$ 6; 44; (44/45); 22; 10; 46; (9/46); 10; <u>6; 44; (44/45); 22;</u> 6; 44; (44/45); 22; 45;

*description, of table, see in text.

If this is so, then for the transmission and registration of information between organisms, with use the telepathy, also, only, two or more signals are required.

3.2. Definition of model components.

As with any sensory system, a system, that receives and transmits information with use the telepathy, requires knowledge of the locations of the receptors that receive the signal, as well as the elements that transmit it back. Such a system, is likely, is formed from several systems – probably, from the 5 SS of the organism. If so, then there, is likely, to be some part (for example, unique type neurons that located, for example, in some sub-region of the B CC) of the system in relation to each SS, of the 5, that can receive and trans-

mit information according to the conditions of the telepathic process. This means that these receptors or third-party elements (components) of communication must be located in these areas. To date, as far as the author knows, such receptors and/or third-party elements have not been discovered.

As an alternative to the hypothesis proposed, above, in work [6], information is provided regarding the sequential activation of BA 6 and the parahippocampal gyrus (paHcGr) (possibly, some parts of BA's 36 (perirhinal cortex) and 37 (visual information processing); since, to a greater extent, information of this type is transmitted in these areas), where the second part of the pathway, probably, receives information with use the telepathy phenomenon. However, the model – the full pathway, is not fully provided. As a

conclusion that can be formed on the basis of information from this work, the telepathy work can occur locally – in the area of the paHcGr, that is located on the border between the part that promotes the accumulation of information regarding autobiography – one's own knowledge (long-term memory, inclusive), and the part – the rest of the B CC, that receives and processes sensory information and occur the work of higher cognitive abilities. If accept as a fact that, in order to explain the phenomenon of telepathy, receptors that receive a signal and transmit it, further, do not exist; the general system, which is supposed to consist of the phenomenon of quantum entanglement, the effect of "mirror neurons", the work of DNA, and, also, probably, auxiliary substances – such as, for example, high quality work of dopamine, that would allow activating the work of a separate nerve cell in order to transmit a signal, then, to the next nerve cells, would allow to explain the work of the telepathy phenomenon, in general..

3.3. General work principle.

Perhaps, under normal conditions, between two organisms there is no transfer of information by telepathy, that is an effect opposite to "magnetism"; perhaps, when the nervous system of one organism is excited to the required high value of the power level, and the other – to a low one – , information is transferred according to the type of the "emitter-collector" system effect.

Figure 2, with the help of an illustration, according to the hypothesis that was proposed, describes, with use of the telepathy phenomenon, the process of information ("image") transfer between two organisms. The

figure has the following description: a and b – graphs that describe, respectively, the relationship of the signal to time and the frequency spectrum of the signal to time; I , t and f – the parameters, that are indicated for the graphs, of the signal values, time and frequency; Object 1 and Object 2 – two objects – organisms, the first of which generates information, and the second – receives it with use of the telepathy phenomenon.

So, most likely, the principle described in the work [6] of the "mentalist's" telepathy is that, with the help of excitation, he specifically activated another area of the B CC, which is not associated with the received of a sensory signal, and in other areas, where the information was to be received, there was an active state, with the help of, possibly, feedback, relaxation – calm wakefulness. Then, the effect of "mirror neurons" was involved; in this case, when the researcher reproduced information for both subjects – the second, of them, did not have, at least, at that moment, the ability to exchange information using telepathy, however, together, with the researcher, they demonstrated the reproduction of the same path of information processing, that did not allow the information to be transferred to the system for further processing. In this case, probably, the "mentalist", with some knowledge about the researcher, could provoke a change in his own "personality", as is achieved with the corresponding mental disorders, for a successful result of copying information that comes from outside, that, in general, improves (or, is) the work of the "mirror neurons" effect.

Figure 2. The proposed telepathy process model. Description, of this, see in the text.

3.4. Source of signal generation.

The effect of "mirror neurons" can be based on the work of the phenomenon of quantum entanglement, that was proposed, for example, in the work [12]. So, the assumption that was formed, above, can be proven by this.

The question is where, exactly, and how a "new" signal arises in the organism.

This, an assumption may arise that, first of all, the action of ionotropic receptors occurs.

First assumption. A side effect, as a change in the thinking process of the organism, can be the state of the air. So, for example, ions that move in the environment that have a positive charge lead to a decrease in the quality of work – the value of the alpha-rhythm power, for example, of the organism, decreases. It might be assumed that information is transmitted in this way by telepathy; however, in the experiment described in [6], an additional "barrier" – another magnetic field, which was generated by a magnetic resonance imaging device, was used. Therefore, the information could, only, be generated inside the organism. Another proof that

this method has a smaller effect is the fact that the organism is not able to perceive difficult information from the air. If the activity of one of the two organisms, which are near to each other, leads to an increase in the number of positively charged atoms in the air, then the other organism will sense this by touch; however, such information, probably, cannot be recognized in full – it is difficult and the method of obtaining it, also, will not allow it to be recognized, at least partially, in the same time interval.

Second assumption. As is known, in the structure of the B CC, there are nerve cells – pacemakers, which do not need an afferent connection from other cells to generate a separate brain rhythm. Such pacemakers, as is known, are controlled by ions (sodium currents) through ionotropic receptors [20]. Since this option, when coupled, together, with the conditions of the experiment from work [6], may be, more, plausible, it should be considered in more detail. Obviously, in this case, the phenomenon of quantum entanglement can be involved. If this phenomenon has a direct connection with the work of DNA, that is given in works [16, 17],

then it is, also, possible that with each DNA mutation procedure, during which activation of quantum entanglement occurs, autonomously, an exchange of information between organisms which have a connection with each other, to a greater or lesser extent, occurs.

3.5. *Work of auxiliary substances.*

In the process of development of the organism, he interacts with other organisms, that leads to mutations of his DNA. Perhaps, such a "connection" has the most important role in occurrence of contact between organisms, in the process of information transfer, in the telepathy.

If so, then, each time, when interacting with a new organism, a "connection" arises between them. Obviously, such a "connection" will be defined as, more, stable, when interacting, with each other, with more time, as well as physical and chemical contact.

As a conclusion from the analysis of known information from works [15, 21, 22], perhaps, when the connection – relationship, with another organism (group of organisms) is broken, there is a release of oxytocin, which provokes improvement of quality of recognition of thoughts (as for example, in the process of the experiment "reading thoughts in the eyes") of other organisms. This can be explained by the protective reaction of the organism to stress, during a period of loneliness, in order to prevent its own death. Thus, an organism which has a greater development in the ability to communicate, in society, probably, feels itself, to a greater extent, lonely.

According to the works [23-25], an increase in the quality of oxytocin and dopamine contributes to an increase in the quality of penis erection; then, it can be assumed that a similar effect occurs in the CNS. Actually, the action of both substances, in this case, is able to maintain a high quality of cognitive abilities. Therefore, if the action of oxytocin is aimed at improving the quality of information recognition, then, probably, the action of dopamine should, in the general system, also, improve this.

In addition, from the materials that are given above, regarding the work of oxytocin and the interactions of the organism with the air state, it can be assumed that there is a connection between this. Perhaps, the work of oxytocin allows to recognize information that was transmitted, specifically, with the help of ions. In addition, there is, also, information regarding the influence of quantities of individual substances – for example, serotonin or D-aspartate, on the occurrence of "noise", that, to a greater extent, can be defined as a hallucination, that is confirmed; however, there are suggestions that, to a lesser extent, this can be determined by information that came from "outside".

3.6. *Conclusion.*

If these hypotheses are true, then it can be assumed that information is transmitted in the form of an "image" – a set of, some, separate parts of the characteristics and memory of one organism to another; and, as a result, with high levels of stress and lack of control over one's own consciousness – low quality work of gamma-aminobutyric acid (GABA), prefrontal cortex and hippocampus, this can lead to a disease such as DID, in that, temporarily, there is a replacement of one's own "personality" with the "personality" of another object (organism, character, etc.). Also, the disadvantage of the result of the telepathy work can be formed a condition under which the "naive" organism, which succumbed to the influence of the phenomenon, can be robbed of: "personality" and/or a separate state of the work of substances (for example, which expresses joy) and/or memory (information of any type), etc., for a certain period of time. As an effect of "vampirism", together, with the help of side effects of the work of substances – for example, endorphin, which have a type of narcotic, such a result can, also, be achieved; in this case, perhaps, the "predator", because of this, is able to increase the productivity of his own, cognitive abilities.

Of course, when influencing the organism, according to the rules of morality, - occurs the advantages of this phenomenon.

3.7. *The impact of the results on future achievements.*

In accordance with the results of the study regarding the formation of a model of information exchange between organisms with use telepathy phenomenon, the following assumptions can be made regarding future achievements in communication and improvement of the technical level.

First, high quality work, separately, simultaneously, of each of the two hemispheres of the brain can contribute to the development of abilities, information exchange, etc. Thus, for example, a method of communication between organisms can be formed, during that information will be transmitted in two streams – using speech and telepathy, simultaneously. Probably, such an effect could be achieved by forming a state, of the brain, in which some areas of the left and right cerebral hemispheres, of the brain, have different proportions of the amounts of substances, when exchanging these, respectively. With the development of the brain, to such a state, of organisms, in several generations, perhaps, in the future, such an effect can be observed. Figure 3 describes this method.

Figure 3. Scheme of the proposed method of communication, in the future.

Secondly, if there is a possibility of receiving, with use of the telepathy, an “image” from another organism, then it can be assumed that the process of teleportation of consciousness at various distances is possible [26]. Since one of the conditions for teleportation of consciousness must be a state in that, over time, the death of the organism is expected; such a result can, obviously, be achieved with use of the telepathy phenomenon, a mental disorder – for example, such as DID, as well as an object that is a “donor”, which can be another organism (including a clone (for example, one that was created using the method (if the technical level allows) of bio-printing) of this organism) or an artificial organism.

4. Conclusions.

Using the analysis of known information and own hypotheses, a model was formed that describes the process of telepathy between organisms. Some of the elements have evidence of this application in the proposed model. However, in general, this requires evidence.

There is a high probability of the presence of telepathic communication, that is reproducible, to a greater or lesser extent, and that depends on a certain state of the systems in each organism.

If the hypotheses are true, then the phenomenon of telepathy can be applied in several models of the development of communication and vital activity of organisms, and the technical level. Perhaps, the study of the telepathy phenomenon will allow a better understanding of the work of quantum physics phenomena – quantum entanglement and corpuscular-wave dualism. In the work, previously, it was not indicated in relation to the second phenomenon, however, perhaps, there is still a place for this.

Information sources list

1. Tomashuk A. S. Information for Forming a Model of Artificial Intelligence, Which Describes the Work of the Human Central Nervous System / A. S.

Tomashuk // Colloquium-journal. – 2022. – Vol. 17. – Is. 140. – 30–45 pp.

2. Tomashuk A. S. Some information about a structure of parts of the central nervous system / A. S. Tomashuk // Colloquium-journal. – Vol. 27. – Is. 186. – 44–72 pp.

3. Wikipedia. Telepatiya [Elektronnyy resurs]. – 2024. – Rezhim dostupa: <https://www.ru.wikipedia.org/wiki/Телепатия> (data poslednego vizita: 04.10.24)

4. Wikipedia. Telepathy [Electronic resource]. – 2024. – URL: <https://www.en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Telepathy> (last date access: 04.10.24)

5. Hosseini E. Brain-to-Brain Communication: The Possible Role of Brain Electromagnetic Fields (As a Potential Hypothesis) / E. Hosseini // Heliyon. – 2021. – Vol. 7. – Is. 3. – e06363.

6. Investigating Paranormal Phenomena: Functional Brain Imaging of Telepathy / G. Venkatasubramanian, P. N. Jayakumar, H. R. Nagendra, D. Nagaraja, R. Deeptha and B. N. Gangadhar // International Journal of Yoga. – 2008. – Vol. 1. – Is. 2. – 66–71 pp.

7. Social Network Position is a Major Predictor of Ant Behavior, Microbiota Composition, and Brain Gene Expression / T. Kay, J. Liberti, T. O. Richardson, S K. McKenzie, C. A. Weitekamp, C. La Mendola, M. Rüegg, L. Kesner, N. Szombathy, S. McGregor, J. Romiguier, P. Engel and L. Keller; ed. L. Chittka // Public Library of Science Biology. – 2023. – Vol. 21. – Is. 7. – e3002203.

8. Beyer A. Schizophrenic Voices as Spirit Communication and Telepathy / A. Beyer // Psychosis. – 2021. – Vol. 13. – Is. 2. – 188.

9. Erickson D. L. Intuition, Telepathy, and Interspecies Communication: A Multidisciplinary Perspective / D. L. Erickson // NeuroQuantology. – 2011. – Vol. 9. – Is. 1. – 145–152 pp.

10. Tonguc B. Quantum Entanglement and Mind to Mind Connection / B. Tonguc [Electronic resource].

- 2015. – URL: <https://www.isites.info/PastConferences/ISITES2015/ISITES2015/papers/A17-ISITES2015ID251.pdf> (last date access: 06.10.24)
11. Psychology Today. The Biology of Telepathy / S. Pillay [Electronic resource]. – 2018. – URL: <https://www.psychologytoday.com/us/blog/debunking-myths-the-mind/201804/the-biology-telepathy?amp> (late date access: 06.10.24)
12. Zac M. From Quantum Entanglement to Mirror Neuron / M. Zac // *Chaos, Solutions & Fractals*. – 2007. – Vol. 34. – Is. 2. – 344-359 pp.
13. Shan G. A Primary Quantum Model of Telepathy / G. Shan // *Social Science Research Network*. – 2003.
14. Shan G. A Primary Quantum Model of Telepathy / G. Shan // *The Parapsychological Association Convention*. – 2004. – 413-421 pp.
15. Oxytocin Improves “Mind Reading” in Humans / G. Domes, M. Heinrichs, A. Michel, C. Berger and S. C. Herpertz // *Biological Psychiatry*. – 2007. – Vol. 61. – Is. 6. – 731-733 pp.
16. MIT Technology Review. Quantum Entanglement Holds DNA Together, Say Physicists [Electronic resource]. – 2010. – URL: <https://www.Technologyreview.com/2010/06/28/91041/quantum-entanglement-holds-dna-together-say-physicists/amp> (last date access: 08.10.24)
17. Quantum Entanglement Between the Electron Clouds of Nucleic Acids in DNA / E. Rieper, J. Anders and V. Vedral [Electronic resource]. – 2011. – URL: <https://arxiv.org/abs/1006.4053> (last date access: 08.10.24)
18. The Brain’s Voices: Comparing Nonclinical Auditory Hallucinations and Imagery / D. E. J. Linden, K. Thornton, C. N. Kuswanto, S. J. Johnston, V. van de Ven and M. C. Jackson // *Cerebral Cortex*. – 2011. – Vol. 21. – Is. 2. – 330-337 pp.
19. A Functional MRI Study of Mental Image Generation / M. D’Esposito, J. A. Detre, G. K. Aguirre, M. Stallcup, D. C. Alsop, L. J. Tippet and M. J. Farah // *Neuropsychologia*. – 1997. – Vol. 35. – Is. 15. – 725-730 pp.
20. Le Bon-Jego M. Persistently Active. Pacemaker-Like Neurons in Neocortex / M. Le Bon-Jego and R. Yuste // *Frontiers in Neuroscience*. – 2007. – Vol. 1. – Is. 1. – 123-129 pp.
21. Reading the Mind in the Infant Eyes: Paradoxical Effects of Oxytocin on Neural Activity and Emotion Recognition in Watching Pictures of Infant Faces / A. Voorthuis, M. M. E. Riem, M. H. Van IJzendoorn and M. J. Bakermans-Kranenburg // *Brain Research*. – 2014. – Vol. 1580. – 151-159 pp.
22. The Two Faces of Oxytocin / T. DeAngelis [Electronic resource]. – 2008. – URL: <https://www.apa.org/monitor/feb08/oxytocin> (last date access: 11.10.24)
23. Hull E. M. Male Sexual Behavior / E. M. Hull and G. Rodriguez-Manzo // *Reference Module in Neuroscience and Biobehavioral Psychology*. – Elsevier, 2017.
24. Baskerville T. A. Interactions Between Dopamine and Oxytocin in the Control of Sexual Behaviour / T. A. Baskerville and A. J. Douglas // *Progress in Brain Research*. – 2008. – Vol. 170. – 277-290 pp.
25. Dopamine, Erectile Function and Male Sexual Behavior from the Past to the Present: A Review / M. R. Melis, F. Sanna and A. Argiolas // *Brain Sciences*. – 2022. – Vol. 12. – Is. 7. – 826.
26. Javadi A.-H. Neuroscience: Teleporting Mind into Body and Space / A.-H. Javadi and H. J. Speirs // *Current Biology*. – 2015. – Vol. 25. – Is. 11. – 448-450.